

EFFECTIVENESS OF MODERN EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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***Abstract.** This article examines the effectiveness of modern educational technologies in higher education institutions. It discusses various pedagogical methods such as problem-based learning, multi-level learning, project-based learning, and the use of information and communication technologies (ICT). The article highlights how these innovative approaches contribute to improving the quality of education, fostering students' cognitive and creative skills, and promoting individualized learning paths. The integration of health-saving technologies and innovative assessment systems like portfolios is also analyzed. Overall, the study demonstrates that the application of diverse educational technologies enables educators to optimize learning time and achieve high student performance.*

***Keywords.** Modern educational technologies, higher education, problem-based learning, project-based learning, multi-level learning, information and communication technologies (ICT), innovative assessment, health-saving technologies, individualized learning, pedagogical methods.*

The word “technology” originates from the Greek words: “techne” – art, craft, skill, and “logos” – science, law. Literally, “technology” means the science of skill. To realize the cognitive and creative activity of students in the educational process, modern educational technologies are used, which allow improving the quality of education, more efficiently using study time, and reducing the amount of reproductive activity of students by minimizing the time spent on homework. In schools, a wide range of educational pedagogical technologies are applied in the learning process. Innovative pedagogical technologies are interconnected,

interdependent, and form a specific didactic system aimed at fostering values such as openness, honesty, kindness, empathy, mutual assistance, and meeting the educational needs of each student according to their individual characteristics.

Pedagogical Technologies

Achieved Results

Problem-based learning

Creation of problem situations in learning and organizing active independent work by students to solve them, leading to creative mastery of knowledge, skills, and development of thinking abilities.

Multi-level learning

The teacher can assist weaker students and pay attention to stronger ones; stronger students advance faster and deeper, while weaker students experience academic success, increasing learning motivation.

Project-based learning

This method allows developing individual creative abilities of students and encourages more conscious professional and social self-determination.

Research methods in learning

Enables students to independently supplement their knowledge, deeply understand the studied problem, and suggest solutions, which is important in forming a worldview and defining individual development trajectories.

Lecture-seminar-exam system

Mainly used in senior classes to prepare students for university studies; concentrates material into blocks and delivers it as a whole, with control based on students' preparation.

Use of game methods in learning business, and other abilities.

Expands horizons, develops cognitive activity,

forms practical skills, and enhances general learning

and other abilities.

Pedagogical Technologies

Achieved Results

educational games)

Cooperative learning (teamwork, group work)

Information and communication technologies (ICT)

Health-saving technologies

Innovative assessment system “portfolio”

Collaboration is viewed as a joint developmental activity of adults and children; individual approach means starting from the child’s abilities rather than the subject, using psychological and pedagogical personality diagnostics.

Enriches educational content, uses integrated courses, and provides internet access.

Allow balanced distribution of different tasks during lessons, alternate cognitive activities with physical exercises, regulate the presentation of complex material, and allocate time for independent work, positively impacting learning outcomes.

Forms a personalized record of student achievements as a tool for pedagogical support, social self-determination, and defining the trajectory of individual development.

Using a wide range of pedagogical technologies enables the teaching staff to productively use study time and achieve high student learning outcomes.

Problem-Based Learning Technology. Problem-based learning technology is based on the theoretical ideas of the American philosopher, psychologist, and educator John Dewey. Today, it is understood as an organization of lessons that involves the creation of problem situations by the teacher and active independent student activity to resolve them, resulting in creative mastery of professional knowledge, skills, abilities, and development of thinking. The goal of problem-based technology is to acquire knowledge, skills, and habits (ZUN), master

methods of independent activity, and develop cognitive and creative abilities. Problem-based learning creates a special kind of motivation — problem motivation, requiring appropriate construction of didactic material, presented as a chain of problem situations.

Problem methods involve creating problem situations and active cognitive student activity, consisting of searching for and solving complex questions that require knowledge activation, analysis, and the ability to see phenomena and laws behind isolated facts.

Modern theory distinguishes two types of problem situations: psychological and pedagogical. The first concerns student activity, the second relates to organizing the learning process. Pedagogical problem situations are created using activating actions and teacher questions emphasizing novelty, importance, beauty, and other distinguishing qualities of the knowledge object. Psychological problem situations are highly individual and must neither be too difficult nor too easy.

Problem situations can be created at all stages of the learning process: explanation, reinforcement, control.

Multi-level Learning. Multi-level learning is a pedagogical technology organizing the learning process with different levels of material mastery. Groups A, B, and C correspond to different depths and complexities of the same material, allowing each student to master subjects at various levels but not below the basic one, depending on abilities and individual traits.

The educational trajectory scheme treats students' efforts and creative application as assessment criteria. Topics required by educational standards remain uniform for all levels. For example, a student from group A studies math at an intermediate level with a group B student but attends advanced Russian classes with group C students and basic-level foreign language with group D students. Transition between levels is possible and smooth, as content remains consistent across groups.

Project-Based Learning Technology. Project-based learning, often referred to as the project method, gained popularity after the publication of V.H. Kilpatrick's brochure "The Project Method: The Use of the Purposeful Activity in Education." In the 1920s and early 1930s, this method was widely used in Russian schools to foster student development. The original slogan was "All from life, all for life."

Karl Frey, in his book "The Project Method," describes 17 distinctive features of the method, including project initiative from real life, mutual agreement on learning form, developing and communicating the project, organizing work, information sharing, and discussion.

The project method represents a system of actions between teachers and students in project development. The goal is to create conditions where students:

Independently and willingly acquire missing knowledge from various sources,

Learn to use acquired knowledge to solve cognitive and practical problems,

Develop communication skills working in groups,

Develop research skills (problem identification, data collection, observation, experimentation, hypothesis building, generalization),

Develop systemic thinking.

Key theoretical positions include:

Focus on the student and fostering creative abilities,

Educational process based on activity meaningful to the student rather than subject logic, increasing motivation,

Individual pace in project work ensuring personal development,

Comprehensive approach supporting balanced physiological and psychological development,

Deep, conscious mastery of basic knowledge through its universal use in various situations.

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